

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE CREATION, SUPPORT, AND DEVELOPMENT OF MOTIVATION IN PROMOTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19679583>

Abstract. *This article scientifically analyzes the concept of incentive as a process of forming motivation, supporting employees and ensuring their professional and personal development. In modern management conditions, incentive has become a complex system that is not limited to material rewards, but also includes spiritual, social and psychological factors. The study reveals the impact of incentive on motivation, its role in organizational effectiveness and practical significance. Also, proposals are developed to improve effective incentive mechanisms based on foreign and domestic experience.*

Keywords: *Encouragement, motivation, human factors, management, employee performance, development, support.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada rag'batlantirish tushunchasi motivatsiyani shakllantirish, xodimlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularning kasbiy hamda shaxsiy rivojlanishini ta'minlash jarayoni sifatida ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy menejment sharoitida rag'batlantirish faqat moddiy mukofotlar bilan cheklanib qolmasdan, balki ma'naviy, ijtimoiy va psixologik omillarni ham o'z ichiga olgan murakkab tizimga aylangan. Tadqiqotda rag'batlantirishning motivatsiyaga ta'siri, uning tashkilot samaradorligidagi o'rni va amaliy ahamiyati ochib beriladi. Shuningdek, xorijiy va mahalliy tajriba asosida samarali rag'batlantirish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish bo'yicha takliflar ishlab chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Rag'batlantirish, motivatsiya, inson omili, boshqaruv, xodimlar samaradorligi, rivojlanish, qo'llab-quvvatlash.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье научно анализируется концепция мотивации как процесса формирования мотивации, поддержки сотрудников и обеспечения их профессионального и личностного развития. В современных условиях управления мотивация стала сложной системой, которая не ограничивается материальными вознаграждениями, но также включает в себя духовные, социальные и психологические факторы. Исследование выявляет влияние мотивации на мотивацию, ее роль в организационной эффективности и практическое значение. Также разработаны предложения по совершенствованию эффективных механизмов мотивации на основе зарубежного и местного опыта.*

Ключевые слова: *Мотивация, мотивация, человеческий фактор, управление, производительность труда, развитие, поддержка.*

Introduction. In a market economy, the sustainable development of organizations and enterprises largely depends on the human factor, that is, the attitude, responsibility and activity of employees to work. In the modern competitive environment, while technologies, financial resources and innovations are gaining importance, it is human capital that is emerging as the main strategic

advantage of the organization. And the full realization of the potential of employees is impossible without effective management and a sound incentive system.

Motivation is an important management tool for increasing employee productivity, directing them towards the general goals of the organization, and increasing their interest in the work process. Motivation is not limited to material rewards or salary increases, but also includes factors such as recognition, creating opportunities for professional development, social support, and improving the psychological environment. Such a comprehensive approach creates positive motivation in employees and strengthens their commitment to work.

Incentives are the process of creating, maintaining, and continuously developing motivation. While initial incentives attract employees to work, consistent and fair incentives stabilize their motivation and encourage professional growth. As a result, employees strive not only to complete assigned tasks, but also to show initiative, be creative, and actively work in the interests of the team.

Therefore, the formation of an effective incentive system in modern management is one of the urgent issues. Each organization should develop flexible and fair incentive mechanisms, taking into account the characteristics of its activities, staff composition and strategic goals. Such an approach, while ensuring the long-term development of the organization, serves to fully realize the human factor.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In scientific literature, the issues of encouragement and motivation are widely covered as one of the important research areas of management and psychology. These concepts are of great importance in the effective organization of employees' labor activities, the formation of their attitude to work, and increasing the effectiveness of the organization. At different times, scientists have explained the sources of motivation, incentive mechanisms, and their impact on human behavior based on various theoretical approaches.

In particular, according to the theory of the hierarchy of needs developed by Abraham Maslow, human behavior is directed towards satisfying the following sequential needs: physiological, safety, social, esteem, and self-actualization. An analysis of the existing literature on marketing shows the need to improve modern marketing principles, brand promotion methods and a flexible approach to consumer requirements. In his textbook on marketing strategies, the expert R. G. Ibragimov states the following: "Marketing strategy is understood as the use of a model of the principles of the enterprise's behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its success." Many economists have been involved in the development and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Bayer.

While the research in the field of marketing conducted in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R. Ibragimov, Y. O. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva and others.

Research methodology. This study used an analytical method. Through this method, the concepts of incentive and motivation were studied in depth based on scientific sources and their content and essence were systematically analyzed. Scientific literature, research on management theories and practical views were analyzed, and the role of incentive in creating, supporting and developing motivation was identified.

Using the analytical method, material and non-material forms of motivation were considered separately, and their impact on employee behavior and labor efficiency was evaluated on a logical basis. This method made it possible to reveal the internal mechanisms of the motivation process, draw theoretical conclusions, and develop scientifically based proposals.

Analysis and results. The conducted analyses show that an effectively organized incentive system significantly increases employees' interest in work, creates a positive psychological climate within the team, and improves the effectiveness of the organization's activities. Incentives are an important management mechanism that not only involves employees in the labor process, but also increases their professional activity, initiative, and level of responsibility.

According to the results of the analysis, forms of material incentives - wages, awards, bonuses and additional payments - play an important role in ensuring short-term motivation of employees. In particular, rewards linked to labor results create a sense of justice in employees and encourage them to complete assigned tasks within the established deadlines. However, relying solely on material incentives may not produce the expected effect in the long term, because over time, material incentives become habitual for employees and their motivational effect decreases.

Intangible incentives play an important role in forming and maintaining internal motivation of employees in the long term. Recognizing employees' work, expressing confidence in them, creating opportunities for career growth, improving qualifications and creating conditions for professional development strengthen employees' sense of loyalty and responsibility for their work. As a result, employees work not only for material benefit, but also for the purpose of self-expression, finding their place in the team and professional growth. Analysis shows that the combination of tangible and intangible incentives gives the highest efficiency. If the incentive system is formed taking into account the individual needs and interests of employees, motivation will be stable and continuous. In such conditions, employees strive to take the initiative, put forward innovative ideas and actively participate in achieving collective goals.

In general, the results of the analysis confirm that motivation is not only a process of creating motivation, but also a process of constantly supporting and developing it. An effective incentive system serves to strengthen the internal environment of the organization, fully realize the potential of employees, and ensure the long-term competitiveness of the organization.

Based on the results of the study, it can be noted that improving the incentive system in organizations is an important condition for the development of human-oriented management. In this regard, it is advisable to organize the incentive process as a comprehensive system that covers not only material rewards, but also the spiritual and professional needs of employees. In particular, recognizing the work of employees, supporting their initiative and creativity, and expanding opportunities for professional development ensure the stability of motivation. It is also necessary to take into account the individual characteristics, level of qualification and personal needs of employees when developing incentive mechanisms. A flexible and fair incentive system creates an atmosphere of trust between employees and strengthens teamwork. This contributes to the improvement of the internal environment of the organization and increases management efficiency.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, motivation is an integral and important component of the modern management system as a process of creating, supporting and continuously developing motivation. In a market economy and in conditions of strong competition, the effectiveness of organizations directly depends not only on material resources or technological capabilities, but also on the internal

motivation, professional activity and initiative of employees. From this point of view, well-thought-out and systematically implemented incentive mechanisms are one of the main factors of the sustainable development of the organization.

An effective incentive system not only forms a positive attitude of employees towards their work, but also helps them to fully realize their professional potential. The combination of material and non-material incentives enhances the sense of responsibility, loyalty and involvement in the goals of the organization. As a result, employees begin to perceive their duties not just as a task, but as an important part of personal development and overall success. Also, the continuous and fair implementation of incentives creates a healthy socio-psychological environment within the organization, strengthens teamwork and reduces personnel turnover. This leads to high labor productivity, increased innovative activity and competitiveness. Therefore, each organization should approach the issue of incentives as a priority in its development strategy and constantly improve it in accordance with the requirements of modern management and the real needs of employees.

References

1. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 166 dated 29.03.2021.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. The rule of law and the protection of human interests are the key to the country's development and the well-being of the people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.- 48 p.
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build a great future with our brave and noble people. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.- 488 p.
4. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. January 24, 2020. - People's Speech, January 26, 2020.
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
6. Azimovna, MS (2022). Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. Formation of psychology and pedagogy as interdisciplinary sciences, 1(9), 20-23.
7. Musayeva, S., & Usmanov, F. (2022). Ways to develop marketing activities in tourist organizations. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 84-88.
8. Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). Issues of improving productivity competition in agriculture. Online scientific journal of innovation in social sciences.-2022.-C, 51-53.
9. Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). The role of marketing in increasing the economic efficiency of service enterprises.
10. Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). The concept of a correct marketing policy in trade and service enterprises.
11. Musayeva, S. (2022). Studying the organization of advertising activities of goods at "Samarkand tea packaging factory" JSC. Science and innovation, 1(A6), 185-192.
12. Musayeva, S. (2022). Prospects for the development of "stekloplastik" llc activity in the conditions of the market economy. Science and innovation, 1(A6), 539-546.
13. Azimovna, MS, Ilkhomovna, UD, & Shokhrukhovich, UF (2022). Importance and Characteristics of Brand Choice in Services. European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science, 1-3.

14. 14.Musaeva Sh. A. Marketing research. Textbook Publishing and creative department of “STAR-SEL” LLC. Samarkand–2023
15. Musaeva Sh. A. Integrated marketing communication. Textbook. "Mahorat" publishing house, Samarkand -2022.